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SPECIFIC METHODS OF TREATING CEREBRAL PALSY

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ABSTRACT

There are many unique aspects of the treatment of cerebral palsy, in which only the constant long-term continuation of a multidisciplinary comprehensive rehabilitation program brings relief to the patient and improves his quality of life. If the patient can take care of himself, this is a great achievement for society and, of course, for his family. The direct active participation of the patient in this rehabilitation increases the effectiveness of this method. The help of psychologists in this is certainly invaluable. With the joint support of several specialists, it is possible to prepare the patient for an active life and increases the patient's interest in life.

Key words: active participation, interest in life, effective method, participation of specialists, rehabilitation measure.

СПЕЦИФИЧЕСКИЕ МЕТОДЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ДЕТСКОГО ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНОГО ПАРАЛИЧА

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Существует множество уникальных аспектов лечения ДЦП, при которых только постоянное длительное продолжение мультидисциплинарной комплексной программы реабилитации приносит облегчение больному и повышает качество его жизни. Если пациент сможет позаботиться о себе, это большое достижение для общества и, конечно же, для его семьи. Непосредственное активное участие пациента в этой реабилитации повышает эффективность этого метода. Помощь психологов в этом, безусловно, неопределима. При совместной поддержке нескольких специалистов создается возможность подготовить пациента к активной жизни и повышается интерес пациента к жизни.

Ключевые слова: активное участие, интерес к жизни, эффективный метод, участие специалистов, реабилитационное мероприятие.

Introduction: Cerebral palsy develops as a result of brain damage in utero, during childbirth, and also during the newborn period, when the main structures of the brain are still immature. The goal of rehabilitation is the physical and social adaptation of the patient and the expansion of his individual capabilities. Rehabilitation in a clinical setting once or twice a year does not bring visible results. That's why we decided to do physical exercises at home together with mothers. Parents can heal their child, not another doctor. Parents have to take care of a child with cerebral palsy all day. With exercise, we want to have a healing and restorative effect on the body to restore performance; improve blood circulation and metabolic processes in the affected area to eliminate or reduce neurovascular and metabolic diseases, prevent the formation of adhesions between the nerve sheath and surrounding tissues, and, if these adhesions exist, to maintain healthy development of the ability of loose tissues to adapt to adhesive formations. ; strengthen weakened muscles, restore coordination of movements, fight related diseases: vertebral curvature and limited mobility.[2]

Research methods: This work is based on the results of a study of 84 patients with various forms of cerebral palsy. Children's age is from 1 to 4 years. We divided them into two groups. First 32 children - 50%; second 32 children - 50%. Both groups received standard treatment, massage, physical therapy. In addition to these treatments, we prescribed home physical therapy to the control group. We have taught parents to continue these exercises at home. Individual exercises were given to each child. We have outlined simple, effective methods that every child should do on a regular basis. Physical procedures consist of hot packs, paraffin

applications, which are performed to prevent joint stiffness. Medicines used in cerebral palsy improve blood circulation and thereby improve the nutrition of muscle and nerve tissue. On the one hand, there is no treatment that can restore the damaged brain.[3] However, if you follow a scientifically based program, then an intact nervous system can perform all its functions. It is very important that exercise therapy sessions begin after the birth of the child, with gradual complications. In addition, even if the child does not have symptoms of cerebral palsy, even if it is prone to its development, classes should be started. Physical education programs play a leading role in comprehensive rehabilitation of children with cerebral palsy. We carefully analyzed the characteristics of the motor environment of each patient with cerebral palsy and created a program that allows to stimulate motor function. [1] When creating a set of exercises for patients with cerebral palsy, attention should be paid to muscle movements. Cerebral palsy patients lack sensory power and this can be corrected to some extent by an exercise program. We worked with the following exercises:

- Muscle stretching exercises: relieves muscle tension, prevents teratogenesis, increases range of motion
- .-Exercises to develop muscle sensitivity, to create strength that allows you to regulate a certain area of muscles
- .-Exercises to improve the functional state of nerve tissue by training nerve sensitivity
- .- Endurance exercises to maintain the efficiency of the organs.
- Relaxation exercises to relieve spasms, tension and cramps.
- Walking exercises (to learn to walk normally).[2]
- Climbing exercises to improve balance and motor strength
- .-Resistance Exercise: Gradually increase resistance exercise to build muscle strength.

Duration of lessons - for young children - 2-3 times a day no more than 15 minutes; 3-4 times a day for 20-30 minutes for children of middle and older age. People with cerebral palsy can develop muscle strength by gradually increasing the intensity of exercise.[5] To ensure that the center of gravity is evenly distributed on both sides of the body, the exercises were performed first with one leg and arm, then with the other. More load was placed on the weakened part, and therefore the movement was improved. We specially developed exercise therapy exercises for cerebral palsy, which allowed us to develop and strengthen the patient's motor skills. We performed a series of exercises necessary to develop and strengthen the abdominal muscles.

We made sure that all actions are performed correctly, because they are remembered, become a habit and become a condition for self-sufficiency. Success depends almost entirely on the parents, because a doctor, physiotherapist or massage therapist can perform the procedures correctly, but they can take very little time. Parents should prepare the child for independent life as much as possible, using special methods at home.[6] Based on the diagnosis of cerebral palsy, clinical presentation, taking into account the type of disease, the patient's age and the severity of the condition, we prescribed massage, physiotherapy and drug treatment. In addition to physical exercises, a lifestyle regimen was added, in which orthopedic aids are used, and step-by-step training with a speech therapist.

Research results: Because with cerebral palsy, muscle tone is disturbed, which later leads to the formation of pathological motor reactions, difficulties in maintaining balance and resisting gravity. In the future, this also leads to the formation of contractures and deformations of the limbs. One of the most effective and efficient means of rehabilitation is home exercise therapy for children with cerebral palsy.[7] The groups that continued physical therapy at home helped to develop the child's ability to inhibit and control their movements. Exercises improve coordination and increase range of motion. Through long-term physical therapy, we help the child develop household skills, knowledge of basic work activities, self-care without parental assistance, development of new skills, as well as proper taught movements.[5] We have based exercise therapy on a number of principles: - regular and systematic exercise; - absence of long breaks; - gradual increase in physical activity; - no referral to other patients - only individual methods; - taking into account the stage of development of the disease, the age of the child, his psychological state.

Together with the parents, we carried out corrective-inflammatory work, which allowed us to compensate for the broken functions. It is recommended to conduct training from an early age. The sooner the better for the child. It is necessary to develop fine motor skills of hands. Materials can be: cones, branches, stones, leaves, fruits and vegetables.

Treatment with physical exercises had a healing effect on the general condition of the body. It helped to strengthen tissues and organs in the child's body. It activated weakened muscles, corrected spinal curvature, improved metabolism and other metabolic processes, activated brain activity and accelerated blood circulation. If the child has difficulty in walking on his own or does not walk on his own, training began near bars or hard supports, and then moved from a hard rope to a weakened

one. We have created an individual rehabilitation treatment program. It is based on modern technologies of motor skill development using innovative technical means - simulators, devices and hardware-software systems.[5] We selected a rehabilitation program for cerebral palsy separately, but physical therapy was mandatory in each complex. With physical therapy, we tried to restore natural motor functions and the child's mastery of basic movements. Together with other methods, physical education helped to achieve the main goal - to provide the child with a full life.[6]

Exercise therapy against cerebral palsy in clinical and home conditions made it possible to achieve the following results:

- basic skills and abilities of the baby are developed;
- decrease in muscle tension;
- increased joint flexibility and range of motion;
- improved balance and coordination
- strengthening the cardiovascular system;
- reducing the frequency and complete elimination of spasms and convulsions;
- increased sensitivity of the nervous system;

Special attention was paid to proper nutrition for children. Basically, children with this diagnosis can be given everything: fruits, vegetables, meat, fish. It is especially important to provide milk for such children. These children especially need love and attention. Only this can cure them. Mothers should walk more in the fresh air. You need to mentally imagine how the disease will rise to the highway and pass. They forced mothers to leave their children in contact with nature as often as possible.

Physical activity had a special stimulating effect on the body, which could ensure its full functioning. During physical exercise, the level of excitation of motor areas of the central nervous system increased significantly.[2] Foci of excitation appeared in them, which contributed to the disappearance of the mechanisms that were the cause of the pathological process. In other words, the painful focus, as if blocked, and as a result, the functions that were disturbed gradually return to normal. Regular exercise combined with standard treatment methods not only helped to get rid of pain, but also helped to normalize seemingly irreversible pathological processes. Therapeutic gymnastics provided natural relaxation of the spine with simultaneous muscle training and is part of the entire therapeutic complex. The exercises had a psychotherapeutic effect.

Light and painless movements improved well-being and had a hardening effect.[5]

Summary. Expected end results: Exercise should definitely be done at home with mom. These exercises strengthen children's health, form the right attitude to a healthy lifestyle; forms moral values: kindness, compassion, sensitivity, friendship; develops children's independent activity skills.[7] The main thing in our business is not to be lazy, but to firmly pursue our goal.

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